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Effect Of Capital Structures On Profitability Of Quoted Cement Companies In Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The study examined the impact of capital structure on profitability of selected cement companies in Nigeria. The study problems were identified and the research questions were raised in connection with the problems statement. The study used an ex- post facto design and the parameters were total debt capital, total equity capital and profit before tax of quoted cement companies in Nigeria. Data were collected from the secondary source. The data were obtained from the financial statements of quoted cement companies, various years 2012-2018. The hypotheses were tested using random effect model technique. The study revealed that, The study revealed that there is a significant positive effect of total debt capital on profitability of cement companies in Nigeria. The study further showed that there is an insignificant negative effect of total equity capital on profitability of cement companies in Nigeria. Additionally, the study shows that there is a significant relationship between capital structure and profitability of cement companies in Nigeria within the period under review. The study recommended that, the quoted cement companies in Nigeria should fund their organisations majorly through debt capital in order to enhance their profits. The quoted cement companies in Nigeria should not consistently use the long-term equity capital in financing their organisations in order to enhance their profits. Also, that quoted cement companies in Nigeria should strike a balance relationship between capital structure and profitability of cement companies in Nigeria as an appropriate mix of long-term debt capital and long-term equity capital to finance their organisations in order to enhance their profit

Keywords: Capital Structure, Profitability, Cement Companies, Debt Capital, Equity Capital

INTRODUCTION

The most important decision all corporate managers should take into consideration is the way in which the long-term capital requirements of their companies should be financed. Capital structure is a term used to represent the proportionate relationship between debt and equity. Many factors have to surface in order to determine the capital structure of a business organization. These factors are what the financial managers consider first in order to determine appropriate capital structure suitable for their firms. Some of the factors are: the cost of capital, flotation costs, and size of the company, government policies and market condition. The combinations of debt and equity have some implications. The first is that debt-equity ratio, which is regarded as an indicator of risk, according to Samuel (1992) has high fixed interest commitment which must be paid by the business organization irrespective of whether profits are made or not. Debt capacity which is the ability of a firm to service its debt payment of interest and principal is usually measured. One of the ways of measuring debt capacity is by raising the ratio of net cash inflow to

interest charges. Pandey (2008) has it that the ratio indicates the number of times the interest obligation is covered by the net cash inflows generated by the company.

The greater the coverage, the lower the risk arising from the debt in the capital structure. Conversely, the lower the coverage the higher is the risk arising from the debt in capital structure. And failure of a company to pay its interests obligation can lead to bankruptcy. Furthermore, just for the business owners, they will employ more of debt in their capital structure as to increase profit. Profitability refers to money that a firm can produce with the resources it has. The goal of most organizations is profit maximization (Niresh & Velnampy, 2014). Profitability is an instrument used in measuring the performance of a firm (Ferah & Nina, 2016) it is one of the main aspects of financial reporting for many firms. Profitability is vital to the firm's manager as well as the owners and other stakeholders that are involved or associated to the firm since profitability gives a clear indication of business performance. (Majed, Said & Firas, 2012). In determining whether to employ more of debt and less of equity or more of equity and less of debt in its capital structure, the financial managers of the firms concerned should take into account, how the capital structure will affect the profitability of their business organization (John, 2015). The profitability of any business organization will determine whether it will remain in business or not especially in the long run. The financial manager must strive to obtain the best financing mix or the optimum capital structure for his or her firm (Pandey, 2008). There are many elements involved in determining the optimal capital mix. The optimal capital mix is achieved when the outlays associated with securing debt financing and the attendant cost of securing equity for any investments are abated. Profitability is usually measured using return on capital employed, return on equity, earnings per share, and return on assets, net profit margin and gross profit margin.

Firms that need finances are faced with dilemma on whether to use debt capital or equity capital. However, it is imperative for firms to know access and manage risks. Firms fail to agree on an optimal capital structure that can effectively accommodate risks and sustain the firm's profitability. The owners of a company will not like to lose the control they have in their company by issuing more shares to the public in order to finance their capital projects. Instead, they resort to borrowing, this means using debt instrument like debenture stock. These owners of the business should not fail to know that whether there is profit or not that the debentures should favour the interest of the business. Nobody can perfectly predict the future, there can be business boom and there can equally be slump in business.

The study about capital structure is a crucial tool used in maximizing company financial performance which is the best interest of shareholders who expects dividends and capital gains from the company. Mansoon (2014) stated that "the decision of capital structure choices is of paramount importance for firms and optimal capital structure is such a mix of debt capital and equity capital that maximizes the firm's value and reduces the weighted average cost of capital". Capital structure decision also helps managers to accomplish their financial strategies like investment and daily operational activities. The argument supported by Toranman, Kilic and Reis (2013) stated that the selection of capital structure components and uses play an important role during the determination of financial strategies of the company. Mireku, Mensah, and Ogoe (2014) also argued that capital structure is strongly linked to the capability of organization to fulfill the expectations of their stakeholders.

Yakubu, Baba and Ibrahim (2016) in their research on capital structure, empirically examined the impact of capital structure on bank profitability in Nigeria. Through this research, evidence has been provided of a positive and significant influence of both owners and borrowed funds in profitability. However, borrowed funds were found to be more prevalent in enhancing the performance of Deposit Money Banks during the period. This research was focused on only the banking sector. By and large, the impact of capital structure in other sectors cannot be overlooked. Irrespective of the fact that a lot of research as have been done on the impact of capital structure in Nigeria, not a lot of emphasis has been placed on the manufacturing sector especially cement companies. It has also been observed overtime that some organizations within the same sectors of the economy perform better than others despite the similarities in the resources available to them in term of assets, human capital and quantity of fund.

This study is therefore, an attempt to check the effect of capital structure and profitability in Nigerian cement companies (quoted) and how such companies combine debt capital and equity capital financing in order to ensure profitability using Dangote Cement plc, United cement company of Nigeria limited and Lafarge cement WAPCO Nigeria plc.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study is to seek the effect of capital structures on profitability of quoted cement companies while the specific objectives are to;

1. analyze the effect of debt capital on profitability of cement companies in Nigeria.
2. determine the effect of equity capital on profitability of cement companies in Nigeria.
3. examine the relationship between capital structure and profitability of cement companies in Nigeria.

Research Questions

This study was guided by the following research questions:

1. What effect does equity capital has on profitability of cement companies in Nigeria?
2. What effect does debt capital has on profitability of cement companies in Nigeria?
3. What is the relationship between capital structure and profitability of cement companies in Nigeria?

Research Hypotheses

The following hypotheses have been formulated to guide the study.

H₀₁: There is no significant effect of long-term debt capital on profitability of cement companies in Nigeria.

H₀₂: There is no significant effect of long-term equity capital on profitability of cement companies in Nigeria.

H₀₃: There is no significant relationship between capital structure and profitability of cement companies in Nigeria.

Literature Review

Capital structure is how a firm will be able to fund its future investment projects through debt, equity, or mixed. Capital structure was defined by Roshan (2009) as a mix of debt and equity capital maintained by a firm. Capital structure refers to a mixture of a variety of long-term sources of funds and equity shares including reserves and surplus of an enterprise. In the words of Omolehinwa (2006), capital structure is the actual mix of debt and equity financing chosen by a particular firm. According to Tulsian (2010), capital structure, that is, financial structure is referred to as the composition of long term funds such as debentures, long term borrowings, preference shares, equity shares, including retained earnings in the capitalization of a company. Pratheepkanth (2011) opined that capital structure refers to a mix of a variety of long term sources of funds and equity shares including reserves and surpluses of an enterprise. There is a sign of stability about the meaning of capital structure as authors consider a mix of debt and equity which forms a company capital structure. Study by Kipesha (2014) with his study on commercial banks in Tanzania, used fixed effect regression model with the help Housman test to measure the relationship between capital structure and banks performance. His results indicated the presence of significant negative relationship between total debt to equity and long term debt to equity with bank cost efficiency and return on equity, something which implies the presence of negative tradeoff between firm leverage and firm performance. The same study indicated a causality relationship between firm leverage and return on asset.

The capital structure of an entity is broadly classified into two major groups, which are: equity capital and debt capital. Equity Capital involves the capability to source external and also issue out equity shares right certified by a share certificate. The equity shareholders own part of the firm. At financial period ending, companies issue dividend to shareholders from the profit made by the firm (Efobi, 2008), while debt capital is the long span obligation an entity applies in funding its investment activities which is accompanied with a long repayment period (Ihenetu, Iwo & Ebiware, 2016). The cost of debt in an entity's capital structure, hinges on the state of its financial position.

There are numerous measures adopted by a firm in gagging its financial performance and arising from this; there is lack of consensus as to the measure or variable which should be applied to proxy performance of a firm. Different measures applied in measuring performance and which have been used by different authors in examining capital structure and profitability include the returns on equity, returns on asset, and earnings per share. The measures are used to determine the contributions of the managers towards the growth and sustainability of the company. Performance is usually measured regarding profitability. Profitability according to Owolabi, & Inyang (2012) is the ability of a company to make profits from all its operations (operating, investing and financing activities). For a firm to make a profit, it must be able to generate revenue more than the direct and indirect costs incurred in generating the revenue. The wealth maximization of shareholders is the ability of a company to witness growth and stable dividend payment or capital gain arising from appreciation in the worth of the firm's market shares. The shareholder's wealth is very important as it determines the investment decisions of the shareholders and as such proper attention should be paid to it by management (Olowe, 2018).

Capital structure makes best use of the market worth of a company that is if a company requiring an appropriately intended capital structures the collective worth of the rights and proprietorship benefits of the stockholders are exploited. Effective and efficient utilization of the capital bring about cost reduction. Appropriate blend of debt and equity enables the company to invest in profitable ventures. This is because capital structure upsurges the capability of the business to find new affluence by generating venture chances. With appropriate wealth gearing it also raises the self-confidence of dealers of debt. This enables a firm to utilize leverage and enjoy the benefits of tax deduction, this leads to an increase in profitability. This is in line with a study conducted by Friend and Lang (1995) who established that there was an affirmative connection between capital structure and profitability. The findings revealed that firms that maintained an optimal capital structure obtained cheap funds to finance their operations which in turn generate returns and enhanced their financial performance.

Capital structure raises the nation's amount of venture and development by growing the company's chance to involve in forthcoming affluence-generating monies. This is because firms that make maximum use of leverage face attractive growth due increasing costs savings as a result as tax deduction. This is consistent with Sakar and Zapatero (2003) who observed there was affirmative connection among leverage and productivity of businesses. Pandey (2008) opined that the financing or capital structure decisions are significant managerial decision. It influences the shareholders return and risk. Consequently, the market value of the shares may be affected by the capital structure decision. The company will have to plan its capital structure initially at the time of its promotion. Subsequently, whenever funds have to be raised to finance investments a capital structure decision is involved. A decision for raising funds generates a new capital structure since a decision has to be made as to the quantity and the form of financing. This decision will involve an analysis of the existing capital structure and the factors which govern the decision at present. The dividend decision is, in a way, a financing decision. The company's policy to retain or distribute earnings affects the owner's claims. Shareholder equity position is strengthened by retention of earnings. This dividend decision has a bearing on the capital structure of the company. The new financing decision of the company may affect its debt-equity mix. The debt-equity mix has implications for the shareholder's earnings and risk, which in turn, will affect the cost of capital and the market value of the firm.

Several empirical studies around the world have been conducted to measure the relationship between capital structure and company profitability. Kipsha (2014) argued that, business firms especially small ones are said to die or poorly perform due to different challenges facing managers on the financing decisions. Due to importance of capital structure decisions on firm performance, studies have conducted to measure its applicability and revealed mixed results. Researcher targeted the previous researchers, those who revealed the positive relationship, those who revealed negative relationship and those who revealed no relation. Mireku (2014) in Ghana listed companies revealed that firm's financial performance has negative relationship with financial leverage and depend more on internal source of finance thus supporting the pecking order theory. Chisti (2013) in listed companies in India discovered that Debt to equity ratio of Indian listed companies was negatively correlated to profitability ratios. This empirical

evidence shows only the negative relationship between the variables without showing the other source of finance which is mostly preferred by Indian Listed companies which might prove the applicability of the capital structure theories. Lavorskyi (2013) in Ukraine conducted a study on the impact of firm performance in Ukraine. Researcher used regression to measure the relationship between the capital structure variable of Leverage ratio against performance variables of Return on assets, total factor productivity (TFP) and EBIT margin. After analyzing the relationship, researcher found that firm leverage was negatively affecting firm performance.

Another study was done by Tailab (2014) in America used a sample of 30 energy American firms for a period of nine years from 2005 to 2013 to test the effect of capital structure on profitability of energy American firms and found the negative relationship between debt ratios and performance variables of return on equity (ROE) and return on asset (ROA) while company size in terms of sales indicated a negative effect only on return on equity (ROE) of the energy American firms. Researcher used multiple regression method to analyze his study data where 10% of ROE and 34% were predicted by independent variables of short term debt, long term debt, total debt to equity ratios and firm size measured by company sales. Another study Leon (2013) was about the impact of capital structure on financial performance of the listed manufacturing firms in Sri Lanka. He used a panel data of 30 listed manufacturing companies from 2008 up to 2012 to measure the relationship between the variables. The data were analyzed and hypotheses were tested using correlation and regression analysis using SPSS. The findings of his study revealed that, there is a significant negative relationship between leverage and return on equity at the same time the relationship between leverage and return on asset showed no relationship.

Nasreem (2013) also tested the relationship between firm's capital structure and financial performance in Pakistan using a sample of 83 companies listed in Karachi stock exchange. Researcher used debt to equity ratio as a measure of capital structure while other ratios like earning per share, price earnings ratio; operating profit margin, return on asset and return on equity were used as proxies for firm performance. After analyzing data using regression model, researcher found that financial performance of a company was significantly affected by their capital structure and their relationship was negative in nature also capital structure showed a negative relation with company market value. Study by Marietta (2012) in Kenya listed companies used multiple regression analytical models to measure the relationship between independent variables of institutional debt and institutional equity as capital structure variables against the dependent variables of ROA and ROE as firm performance variables and revealed that there is a negative relationship between total debt and firm performance. In terms of relationship between equity and firm performance, his study revealed that there is a significant positive correlation between return on equity (ROE) and total equity using Pearson correlation.

Moreover, empirical evidence was shown by Ratheepkanth (2011) in Sri-Lanka listed companies' revealed negative relationship between capital structure and company profitability. The study by Kaaya (2013) about the relationship between capital structure and commercial bank performance in Tanzania concluded that the relationship between these two variables (capital structure and bank performance) was negative and their results were significant at 5% significant level.

Another study conducted by Shubita (2012), measured the relationship between capital structure and profitability of Jordan companies. The researchers used correlations and multiple regression analysis to measure the relationship between variables to reach the intended results. The researcher used ROE as performance variable against capital structure variables of Short term debt to Asset, Long term debt to asset, and total debt to asset as independent variables. The study results showed a negative relation between debt finance and profitability. Their findings implied that an increase in debt position is associated with a decrease in profitability of companies, thus the higher the debt the lower the profitability of the firm. The researcher used only one performance measure of ROE to come up with the conclusion. Toraman (2013) examined manufacturing companies in Turkey and discovered the negative relationship between short term debt to total assets, long term debt to total assets and Return on assets (ROA). He also discovered no significant relationship between total debt to equity ratio and ROA. Researcher used regression model to measure the relationship between capital structure and company profitability using a sample of 28 manufacturing industries.

Another study by Ntogwa (2014) with his study on the influence of capital structure on working capital and growth opportunity of a firm in Tanzania, found that the growth opportunity of listed companies in Tanzania does not depend on the capital structure but depends on the investment opportunity available in that company. Feng (2013) in Sweden listed companies used regressions and correlations models to measure such relationship and revealed the negative relationship between capital structure and corporate performance. Badu (2012) targeted 7 listed banks in Ghana from 2000 to 2010 and tested the relationship between capital structure and banks performance. The regression result of his study indicated that capital structure is inversely related to performance of the listed banks in terms of return on equity. His study used one profitability measure of return on equity to come up with the study results.

Lovorskyi (2013) examined the impact of capital structure on firm performance in Ukraine using regression model and found that, firms leverage ratio had negative impact with performance indicator of return on asset (ROA) at -0.098 confidence level, leverage against earnings before interest and tax (EBIT) at -0.119 and leverage ratio against total productivity factor at -0.458. Other study by Zeitun (2007) in Jordan used a sample of 167 Jordan companies from 1989 to 2003. His study results indicated a negative relationship between firm performance indicator of return on asset with capital structure indicators of total debt to total assets, long term debt to total assets, short term debt to total assets and total debt to total equity. Kayode (2014) in Nigeria conducted a study on the effect of capital structure on firm performance in Nigeria using the panel data of 10 companies from 2003 to 2012. Researcher used descriptive and regression technique was employed to test the relationship between performance variables of return on asset and return on equity against capital structure variables of total debt to total assets, total debt to equity. In his study results he revealed that capital structure was negatively related to firm performance.

Odita (2012) used regression and Pearson correlation to analyze the impact of capital structure on firm performance in Nigeria. He used performance measures of return on assets and return on equity while capital structure measures were debt ratios and controlling variables of asset turnover, firm size, age, asset tangibility and firm growth opportunity. His study results indicated a negative and significant relationship between performance measures of return on assets and return on equity against debt ratio. Alawwad (2013) in Saudi Arabia, used regression technique to measure the relationship between the variables of capital structure against variables of firm performance and found that all levels of debt ratios had inverse relationship with firm performance indicators of return on asset (ROA), return on equity (ROE) and profit margin. Another group of researchers measured the relationship between capital structure and company profitability and revealed the positive relationship between the measurable variables of their studies. Hughes (2013) listed firms in Ghana, discovered a significant positive relationship between short term debt and profitability, negative relationship between profitability and long term debt. The overall results of the study revealed that Ghana firms listed in Ghana stock exchange depended on short term debt than long term debt. Uremagu (2012) Olalebe (2013) and Adesina (2015) in Nigerian companies, their studies revealed that profitability of Nigerian firms depends on capital structure components.

Another study was done by Abiodun (2012) on the effect of optimal capital structure on manufacturing firms performance in Nigeria, used a sample of 10 firms from 2000 to 2009. Researcher used debt ratio as capital structure variable against company performance, and found that there is a relationship between the distribution of debt ratio and corporate performance and their main conclusion was that the manufacturing industries was consistent with trade off theory. That means debt ratio has positive relation with corporate performance. Moreover Soybo (2014) used performance variables of return on assets (ROA) and return on equity (ROE) and capital structure ratios of debt to equity and debt to asset ratios to analyze the relationship between the variables. Correlation coefficient and regression technique used to test a panel data of 10 companies from 2000 to 2011. His study results indicated that the relationship between capital structure and return on asset is not significant across all firms and insignificant relationship was shown between return on equity and debt to asset ratio however the results showed the significant relationship between return on equity and debt to equity ratio for all firms. This justified that a highly geared firm tend to have high profitability.

Zuraidah (2012) in Malaysia, measured the relationship between the capital structure indicators of short term debt, long term debts and total debts against performance indicators of return on assets and return on

equity. Researcher used panel data of 58 firms from 2005 to 2010. The results of the study indicated that only Short term debt and total debt had a significant relationship with return on assets (ROA), other capital structure variables had a significant relationship with return on equity (ROE). Another study showing positive relationship was conducted by Priya (2013) who targeted listed trading companies in Sri-lanka, and analyzed variables using correlation method and come up with the conclusion that debt to asset ratio and debt to equity ratio of listed companies correlated with gross profit margin, net profit, ROCE and ROE at significant level of 0.05 and 0.1 their final conclusion was that, there was a positive relationship between capital structure and financial performance of listed companies in Sri-lanka. Mwangi (2014) targeted non-financial companies listed in Kenya and concluded that, financial leverage had a negative effect on performance as measured by return on equity of non-financial companies listed in the Nairobi stock exchange.

Jaffna (2013) analyzed the impact of capital structure on financial performance of the listed trading companies in Sri Lanka. He used companies data listed in Sri-lanka stock exchange during 2006 to 2010 and came up with the following results. He used correlation analysis and revealed that debt asset ratio and debt equity ratio and correlated with gross profit margin, net profit margin, ROCE, ROA and ROE at significant level of 0.05 and 0.1 Finally their results concluded a positive relationship between capital structure and financial performance. Another analysis was conducted by Pouraghan (2012) who measured Iran companies using Pearson correlations and estimation of multiple regressions models to test independent variables of Debt ratios and controlling variables of firm size, firm age, asset tangibility and growth opportunities against dependent variables of return on assets and return on equity. He then discovered strong negative relationship between debt ratios and performance measures. Moreover, researcher discovered a positive relationship between controlling variables and performance variables of the companies. Other empirical studies have shown mixed results where some study variables shows negative relationship while others revealed the positive relationship. Goyal (2013) with his study on listed public sector banks in India, tested the study variables using regression analysis. The results of his study validated a strong positive dependence of short term debt to capital with all profitability measures of ROA, ROE and EPS while long term debt to capital and total debt to capital had a negative relationship with return on assets (ROA), return on equity (ROE) and Earning per share (EPS).

Mihael (2012) in listed firms in Romania, his results indicates that there was a contradictory as the delivered both in favor of the positive correlation and in favor of negative correlation between the capital structure and firm's performance. Due to this conclusion, it was not clear whether capital structure influenced performance or not, for that case the further study on this relationship has to be conducted. Abbasali (2012) in Tehran used Pearson correlation and multiple regression models to test the relationship between independent variables of debt ratios against dependent variables of return on asset (ROA) and return on equity (ROE). Researcher also used controlling variables of asset turnover, firm size, and asset tangibility and growth opportunity as other independent variables of the study. The results of the study indicated a negative relationship between debt ratio and financial performance. Also, results indicated a significant positive relationship between asset turnover, firm size, and asset tangibility and growth opportunity with financial performance measure.

RESEARCH METHODS

The study adopted *expo facto* research design based on the nature of the data, scope of the study, hypotheses, and technique of data analysis. The population of this study is the entire cement companies in Nigeria that are registered with the corporate affairs commission covering the periods of adoption and implementation of IFRS in Nigeria. This study used purposive sampling technique to select Dangote cement Plc, United Cement Company of Nigeria plc and Lafarge Cement Wapco Nigeria plc for the study. These companies were selected on the basis of being listed on Nigerian stock exchange as at 31st December, 2018 and the availability of their financial statements where data were sourced. The study used Secondary data. The data were drawn from the audited and published financial statements of the selected company (Dangote cement Plc, United Cement Company of Nigeria plc and Lafarge Cement Wapco Nigeria Plc.) that were available within the period of 2012 to 2018. Data collected within the

period of 2012 – 2018 were analyzed and subjected to test using panel regression analysis. In this study, the capital structure is the independent variable while profitability is the dependent variable. Capital structure is represented by Total Debt Capital and Total Equity Capital while profitability is represented by Profit Before Tax (PBT). This is hereby functionally represented as follows:

$$PBT = f(TDBT, TEQTY)$$

This is econometrically expressed as follows:

$$PBT = \alpha_1 + \beta_1 TDBT_{it} + \beta_2 TEQTY_{it} + U_{it}$$

Where:

PBT = Profit Before Tax

TDBT = Total Debt Capital

TEQTY = Total Equity Capital

I = Firms

t = Periods

U_{it} = error term

α_1 = constant

β_1 And β_2 are coefficients to be determined

On a priori basis, $\beta_1 >$

0 and $\beta_2 > 0$.

The study used descriptive statistics, Pearson correlation technique and Hausman test to evaluate the mode. The data were analysed with the aid of Stata 13 software.

RESULTS

The results from the data analysis were presented in this section.

Table 4.1: Descriptive Statistics

Stats	PBT	TDBTC	TEQTYC
Mean	71765.62	3776.19	31010.43
Maximum	306251	8520	152475
Minimum	1187	628	126
Std. Dev.	88862.87	3431.372	41909.73
Skewness	1.10667	0.5750415	1.407502
Kurtosis	3.196826	1.507781	4.274393
Observ.	21	21	21

Source: Researcher's computation using Stata 13 software

Data used for the analysis were sourced from the financial statements of quoted cement companies in Nigeria, consisting of dangote Cement Plc, Lafarge cement WAPCO Nigeria Plc and cement company of Northern Nigeria Plc, various years (2012-2018). Prior to the multiple linear panel regression estimation, an analysis of the descriptive statistics of the variables is embarked upon. It can be observed from Table 4.1 that profit before tax, total debt capital, and total equity capital for the period 2012-2018, showed a mean of ₦71,765.62; ₦3,776.19 and ₦31,010.43 with their standard deviation of ₦88,862.87; ₦3,431.372 and ₦41,909.73 respectively. The descriptive statistics further shows that the minimum profit before tax made by the quoted cement companies with the capital structure mix amounted to ₦1, 187 billion and the maximum profit amounted to ₦306, 251 billion.

Table 4.2: Pearson Correlation

	PBT	LTDBTC	LTEQTYC
PBT	1		
LTDBT	0.9239	1	
LTEQTY	0.3480	0.4119	1

Source: Researcher's computation using Stata 13 software

Considering the results of Pearson correlation in table 4.2 above, there is no problem of serial correlation as the independent variables correlational relationships among themselves are below the coefficient value of 0.85(see hair etal 2005).

Checking for the Appropriate Model of Panel Data for the Research

There are two models of panel data analysis that could be employed in establishing the linear regression equation for research work involving entities over time (i.e. Panel data analysis). The models are fixed effect model (FE) and random effect model (RE). The model to be applied depends on its appropriateness to the research data and the entities involved (Agung, 2014). The main distinction of the two models revolves around the manner in which the individualities and heterogeneities of the entities are treated. Among the statistical approaches to determine their appropriateness to a given research linear regression are hausman test for RE and FE. These are applied in this research to determine the suitable model for the research linear regression equation estimation.

Hausman Test: Random Effect Model versus Fixed Effect Model

The assumption of a random effect model is a constant variance of individual specific effect while fixed effect model accords importance to the heterogeneity of the individual group by establishing intercept for the unobserved variables of the individual group that affect their behaviour or performance over the study period. Hausman is normally used to determine whether there is a correlation between the unobserved effect with the independent variables or not. Hence, Hausman test was used to determine which among the two models is appropriate for this research work. This is as presented in Table 4.3

Table 4.3: Hausman Test for FE and RE

Dependent Variable	Chi-Sq Statistics	Probability	Decision
PBT	1.48	0.4765	accepted

Note: PBT is a profit before tax

Null hypothesis: Random effect model is the appropriate model

Alternative hypothesis: Fixed effect model is the appropriate model

The decision criterion is acceptance of the null hypothesis if the Chi-Square statistics probability values are greater than 5%, but a rejection of the null hypothesis if otherwise. However, from table 4.3 the probability value is above than 5%. The null hypothesis that the random effect model is appropriate was accepted; hence the random effect model is the appropriate model among the two models.

Table 4.4: Coefficients

CPS_TDP	Coefficient	Std. Error	z-Statistics	Prob.
Constant	-17582.69	12005	-1.46	0.143
TDBT	24.34356	2.552656	9.54	.00
TEQTY	-.0831208	.2089995	-0.40	0.69
Adjusted R ²	0.598660			
Wald Chi	105.96			
Prob(F-statistic)	0.0000			

Source: Researcher’s computation using Stata 13 software

The results in table 4.4 above showed that the independent variable of capital structure explained around 60% of the variations in the profitability of Quoted Cement Companies in Nigeria, from the coefficient of determination (adjusted R² of 0.598660). Also, the result of Wald chi value of 105.96 and the corresponding probability value of .00 indicated that the model is fit and admissible for decision making.

4.3 Test of Hypotheses

In order to analyse the impact of capital structure on profitability of quoted cement companies in Nigeria, the following hypotheses were examined using random effect panel least square regression technique.

H₀1: There is no significant effect of total debt capital on profitability of cement companies in Nigeria.

H₀2: There is no significant effect of total equity capital on profitability of cement companies in Nigeria.

H₀₃: There is no significant relationship between capital structure and profitability of cement companies in Nigeria.

The results from table 4.4 above showed that there is a significant effect of total debt capital on profitability of cement companies in Nigeria, from the coefficient of 24.34356 which is significant at 1% level of significance as indicated by (sig. level of 0.00). Based on this, the null hypothesis one is rejected. However, the results from table 4.4 above showed that total equity capital has no significant impact on the profits of quoted cement companies in Nigeria, from the coefficient of -.0831208 which is not significant at all levels of significance as indicated by (sig. level of 0.69). Based on this, the null hypothesis two is accepted. The results from table 4.2 above showed that there is a significant relationship between capital structure and profitability of cement companies in Nigeria as depicted by the correlation values of total debt capital of 0.9239 and total equity capital of 0.3480 respectively. Based on this, the null hypothesis three is rejected.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The study revealed that there is a significant positive effect of total debt capital on profitability of cement companies in Nigeria. All things been equal, ₦1 increase in total debt capital leads to ₦ 24,343.56 value rise in the profits of Quoted Cement Companies in Nigeria for the period under review. This is in line with Abbasali (2012); Goyal (2013); who affirmed that long-term debt is directly related to profitability. Pouraghan (2012) also opined that firms using debt finance earn more profit. However, this finding is in disagreement with the findings of Alawwad (2013) and Odita (2012) who revealed a negative correlation between debt financing and profitability.

The study further showed that there is an insignificant effect of total equity capital on profitability of cement companies in Nigeria. Putting all other variables constant, ₦1 increase in total equity capital brings about ₦ -. 0831208 value decrease in the profits of Quoted Cement Companies in Nigeria for the period under review. This finding is in agreement with Kipesha (2014) who found an insignificant positive relationship between profitability and long-term equity. Lang (1995) also opined that increase in equity capital caused an increase in the profitability of the firms. But, this is in disagreement with Jaffna (2013) who asserted that long-term equity has a negative significant impact on the performance of the firms.

Finally, the study shows that there is a significant relationship between capital structure and profitability of cement companies in Nigeria. This finding is in agreement with Leon (2013; Lavorskyi (2013) who found a significant positive relationship between capital structure and profitability. Mireku (2014) also opined that increase in capital caused an increase in the profitability of the firms. But, this is in disagreement with Ntogwa (2014) who asserted that capital structure has a negative significant impact on the profitability of the firms.

CONCLUSION

The total debt capital has a positive impact on the profits of Quoted Cement Companies in Nigeria as revealed by this study. The quoted cement companies in Nigeria must consider the total debt options in financing the business activities because these will increase the profits of their organisations. The finance managers of the quoted cement companies should ensure a proper balance has to be struck between the need for return and the danger of financial risk. When the shareholders' return is maximised and the financial risk is minimised, the capital structure will be considered optimum. The quoted cement companies in Nigeria must fund their business activities with less equity capital to enhance the company optimum profits as revealed by this study. Financing business activities through new equity capital have will affect the ownership in turn affect block holder ownership of the firm. The consistence increases of the finding of business through equity capital will reduce the profitability of the firm as a result of agency problem.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The recommendations are based on the findings and conclusion of this study as follows:

1. The quoted cement companies in Nigeria should fund their organisations majorly through debt capital in order to enhance their profits.
2. The quoted cement companies in Nigeria should not consistently use the long-term equity capital in financing their organisations in order to enhance their profits.
3. The quoted cement companies in Nigeria should strike a balance relationship between capital structure and profitability of cement companies in Nigeria as an appropriate mix of long-term debt capital and long-term equity capital to finance their organisations in order to enhance their profit.

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